

SUSTAINABLE MECHANISMS FOR PLASTIC WASTE DISPOSAL IN ENUGU METROPOLIS: THE ROLE OF MEDIA CAMPAIGN

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Abstract: The mechanisms for plastic waste disposal in Enugu metropolis are ineffective with people indiscriminately dumping refuse in the open, thereby exposing others to its adverse social, economic, health and environmental impacts. This study was designed to ascertain the role of media campaigns on sustainable mechanisms for plastic waste disposal in Enugu metropolis. Multistage sampling techniques were employed to select the 230 respondents studied; 50 ESWAMA staff and 180 residents of the metropolis. To get info about the sustainable mechanisms for plastic waste disposals and media campaign roles, specific objectives were followed and data analysed using descriptive statistics and Likert scale rating with 3 as the cut-off or decision point. Results indicate that residents travel for about 2km dump their refuse in approved wastebin/dumpsites. It also showed that the frequency of waste collection undecided (54%) and that residents adopts both wastebin and open dump disposal mechanisms. On that note, it was agreed that media campaign plays important role in changing the attitudes of the residents from illegal dumping of refuse to proper refuse dumping practice. Radio broadcast was shown to be the best source of information in the metropolis; however, it was also shown that ESWAMA does not sponsor media campaigns. Factors such as poor wastebins, information, and collection frequency affects waste disposal in the metropolis. Among others, we recommend that ESWAMA as a regulator should sponsor and organize periodic public awareness campaign on radios.

Keywords: Media campaigns, disposal mechanisms, attitudinal change, wastebins, radio broadcast.

Introduction

Plastic is a synthetic or semi-synthetic lightweight, hygienic and resistant material produced through different organic polymers such as nylon, polyvinyl chloride, polyethylene, etc., which can be moulded and utilized in many varieties of ways and applications (UNEP, 2018). They possesses versatile qualities proven to be use in many forms or shape such as biodegradable plastics, modified natural polymers, natural polymer, thermoplastics, and

thermosetting plastics (Andrady & Neal, 2009). Its benefits are undeniable, and the demand is tremendous which has contributed to the boom in production. In the developing countries, plastics are used daily, virtually in every aspect of life; clothing, catering, shopping, footwear, food packaging and public health applications (Andrady & Neal, 2009). According to Flaomo (1995), in developing economy, the generation of plastic waste and disposal are part of its functions. And its generation from both

commercial and domestic sources has significantly grown in the past decade. Every time people shop in a store or market, it contributes to the generation of plastic wastes which contributes to the millions of tons of waste in the environment. The disposal of plastic material contributes to the growth of dirt and litters the environment. Presently, plastic waste has become a growing global concern due to its environmental threats if it is inappropriately collected, disposed or stored (Yoda, Chirawurah, & Adongo, 2014). The uncontrolled disposal of plastic waste can contribute to pollutions; air (when burnt), land (due to its non-degradability in the soil), water (through the contamination of underground water), and drainage and sewage blockage (Tiway, 2015). However, according to (UNEP, 2018), unless we rethink the way we produce, utilize and manage plastics, we will won't be able to cope with the quantity of waste we generate.

In Enugu state, the control of plastic waste has been ineffective. People indiscriminately dumped it in the open particularly on the streets, roads, residential compounds etc., and as a consequence, discomfoting residents due to the offensive, stinking odour emanating from those sites. Thereby, exposing them various kinds of diseases. Therefore, to achieve a sustainable and healthy environment, there is need to fundamentally manage these wastes by adopting proper disposal attitudes. This is because the main issue is not about the unavailability of policies or legislation but poor attitudes towards the environment which leads to poor implantation of environmental policies. There is the need for an environmentally stimulated public enlightenment with the needed courage and intensity to change this pathetic attitude of people towards the environment. People needs to join hands to control waste and its associated health hazards in the state to ensure the attainment of a clean, sustainable and healthy environment for the well-being of all. This therefore forms the major aim of this study to

ascertain the role of media campaigns in changing the attitudes of people towards adopting a sustainable plastic waste disposal mechanism in the metropolis. This would be determined by;

- ascertaining the plastic waste disposal mechanisms adopted by residents,
- ascertaining the extent to which the broadcast media influence people's attitude towards proper plastic waste disposal practices in the metropolis,
- ascertaining the role broadcast media plays in plastic waste management,
- determining the extent to which broadcast media carry out public awareness campaigns on plastic waste management, and
- ascertaining the factors affecting people's change of attitudes to a proper plastic waste disposal.

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Planned Behaviour

This study will be guided by this theory as it borders on the relationship between the behaviours and attitudes of the people of Enugu metropolis towards plastic waste disposal. From this theory, it means that if residents believes that proper plastic waste disposal behaviour is more beneficial than the inappropriate disposal behaviour will change their attitudes by behaving appropriately. Applying this to the media campaign role in bringing proper environmental psychology, it is known that proper disposal behaviour carries positive normative belief, that is to say that, proper plastic waste disposal behaviours are positive behaviours. Although people may have the intention to behave properly, their perceived behavioural control can be hindered by constraints such as a belief that one's behaviour will not have any impact. For instance, when one intends to behave responsibly but lacks proper disposal knowledge or infrastructures, it means that his/her constraints are high because his/her perceived behavioural control is low, so on that note, his/her behavioural change

may not occur. So, to apply this in this contest would help explain the contradictions between proper and improper waste disposal attitudes. This theory of planned behaviour is an important predictive model for explaining people's behaviour. Individual's appraisal of attitudes towards behavioural change are determined through their knowledge about the behaviour. Where knowledge is defined as the subjective probability that the behaviour will produce a certain outcome.

Studies have used the theory of planned behaviour as a framework is not useful for knowing, elucidating and envisaging behaviours but also in providing good guides used in designing strategies for interventions to alter or sustain behaviour (Ifegbesan 2009). This theory has been used widely in studies on environmental behaviour to predict people's participation intent in a specified behaviour (Gamba & Oskamp, 1994; Ifegbesan, 2009:202). This explains why people's environmental perceptions are linked to their actions. Peoples' environmental attitudes can be influenced by their knowledge of the environment. In all, this theory is applied in this study to elucidate that intent is used to predict an individual's attitudinal/behavioural change to either participate in an environmentally friendly activity or not. This points towards a responsible environmentally friendly behaviour, that includes a group or an individual's action taken to do right for the sustainability of the environment. On that note, media campaigns are supposed to educate people on the proper disposal mechanisms which by this theory would engender the needed change in their attitudes towards improper waste disposal behaviours. That is to say that the media campaigns awaken peoples' consciousness to adopt a responsible and sustainable environmental behaviour.

Method

Enugu state is the area for this study particularly the Enugu metropolis which comprises Enugu South, Enugu North and Enugu East Local Government Areas (LGAs) with about 722,664 households. This and the staff of the Enugu State Waste Management Authority (ESWAMA) formed the population for this study where sample was drawn.

To select the areas and respondents studied, we employed multistage sampling technique (table 1). First, we purposively selected two layouts from each of the three LGAs due to their high population. Secondly, two streets were randomly selected from each layout and 15 respondents randomly selected from each of the twelve streets. For ESWAMA staff, 50 staff were randomly selected; 38 junior and 12 senior/management staff thereby making a total sum of 230 respondents studied.

Data was collected by means of a structured questionnaire, administered to the respondents through the help of the research assistants. However, prior to participation, respondents gave their approval by signing the consent form before answering the research questions.

We employed descriptive statistics to analyze variables with observable facts and Likert scale to analyze respondents' attitude towards plastic waste management media campaign. Their responses were graded as follows; 1 for strongly disagree, 2 for disagree, 3 for undecided, 4 for agreed, and 5 for strongly agreed. To get the cutoff point, the total sum of the points (15) was divided by the number of points (5) to get 3. Therefore, any score equal or greater than 3.0 was accepted to be significant, while those below 3.0 was considered as non-significant and therefore rejected.

Table 1: Sampling Summary

LGA	Layouts	Streets	Respondents
Enugu East	Trans-Ekulu	Phase six	15
		Second avenue	15
	Abakpa Nike	Ugbene	15
		Nnaji	15
Enugu North	New Heaven	Upper Chime	15
		Nanka	15
	Asata	Owerri road	15
		Connor	15
Enugu South	Achara	Awkunanaw	15
		Jonah Agbo	15
	Uwani	Zik's avenue	15
		Amawbia	15
Sub Total	6	12	180
ESWAMA	Junior	Senior	
	38	12	50
Total			230

Table 2: Description of Demographic Variables

Variables	Description	Mean	SD
Sex	Male 1; female 0	58.40	12.8
Age	Number of years	28.79	0.7
Education	Formal education 1; otherwise, 0	66.33	5.3
Marital Status	Single 1; otherwise, 0	48.99	2.8
Occupation	Business 1; otherwise, 0	78.03	0.5
Distance to wastebins/dumpsite	Kilometers (km)	1.73	2.2

Source; Field Survey, 2022

Results and Discussion

The results of the demographic variables as shown in table 2 indicates that the average age of the respondents surveyed were approximately 29yrs. They were mostly

males (58%) and educated (66). Approximately 49% of the respondents were single and 78% of them engaged in business for a living. Table 2 also showed that the respondents travel about 2km on the average to the

wastebin/dumpsites. From this, one can infer that the age, education and occupation compositions of the respondents represent a mature and responsible set of individuals that are capable of giving information out of experience.

Table 3: Frequency of waste collection

	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	9	18.00
Weekly	14	28.00
Undecided	27	54.00
Total	50	100

Source; Field Survey, 2022

Table 3 indicates that the frequency of waste collection in the metropolis is undecided (54%) followed by weekly collection (28%). This is not encouraging as it would demoralise inhabitants not knowing when their wastebins would be emptied. It also calls private waste collector as ESWAMA is not living up to the task of collecting waste in the peripheries of the metropolis.

Table 4: Waste disposal mechanism

Disposal Mechanisms	Mean	Decision
Wastebin/dumpsites	3.08*	Accepted
Open dump	3.84*	Accepted
Burning	1.45	Rejected
Gutter dump	2.43	Rejected

Source; Field Survey, 2022

The findings of table 4 indicates that wastebin (3.08) and open dump (3.84) are the two waste disposal mechanisms in the metropolis. However, open dump disposal is the main mechanism having attained the highest rating. This is a worrisome development going by the social, economic, health and environmental impact of open refuse dumping. It would help in defacing the environment, cause different health complications which would take a fortune for inhabitants to treat. This can be avoided if the wastes are properly disposed and collected.

Table 5: The extent to which Broadcast Media Campaigns Contribute to Attitudinal Change towards Plastic Waste Management

Variables	Mean	Decision
Wastebin/dumpsites	4.07	High
Open dump	2.53	Low
Burning	1.20	Low
Gutter dump	2.32	Low

Source; Field Survey, 2022

Table 5 implies that in waste management media campaign contributes on a high extent to the attitudinal change of people from open dump, burning and gutter dumping of refuse to wastebin/dumpsite dumping. This is encouraging as it would help engender proper and healthy environment.

Table 6: Respondents' Perceived Role of Media Campaigns on Proper Plastic Waste Disposal Mechanism

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Significant/vital	109	60.56
Insignificant	71	39.44
Total	180	100

Source; Field Survey, 2022

Table 6 shows that about 61% of respondents believed that media campaigns play a vital role on proper plastic waste disposal mechanism in the metropolis. It helps to engender the right attitudes and knowledge needed for a proper and sustainable waste management in the state. Studies have supported this finding that media campaigns play a vital role in promoting behavioral change towards the environment. According to Koser, R. (2017) and Rim-Rukeh & Ogbemi (2007:493), it can help people to improve their knowledge and partnership between natural resources and the environment. Equally, Kurtycz, (2005) highlighted the need for a better understanding of attitudes, behaviour, environmental principles and waste management theories through communication to enhance people's ability to participate in the daily practices of

plastic waste management. So, environmental campaigns focused on waste management issues plays key role in keeping the public aware of the dangers associated with wastes. Creating adequate awareness on the health and environmental dangers of poor waste handling are key factors needed to be regularly communicated to all (Saxena, 2010; Zurbrugg, 2002).

Do you think that media reporting is enough for public enlightenment on waste management?

Table 7: Level of Media Reportage of Waste management campaigns

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Sufficient	62	34.44
Insufficient	118	65.56
Total	180	100

Source; Field Survey, 2022

In Table 7, about 66% of respondents indicates that media reportage of waste management campaigns in the metropolis is insufficient. Therefore, there is need to explore broadcast media potentials in the fight against indiscriminate waste disposal in the metropolis.

Which source of the broadcast media disseminate information about waste management?

Table 8: Source of Media Campaigns

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Radio	103	57.22
TV	77	42.78
Total	180	100

Source; Field Survey, 2022

In Table 8, about 57% of respondents indicate that their main source of broadcast media campaigns about waste management is radio broadcast. So, radio broadcast is a good source of information for people living in the metropolis.

Do you sponsor the broadcasting of information about waste management?

Table 9: Sponsorship of Media Campaigns

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	19	38.00
No	31	62.00
Total	50	100

Source; Field Survey, 2022

Table 9 implied that ESWAMA does not sponsor media campaigns with 62% of their staff surveyed revealing this anomaly. It is important to sponsor media campaign and advertisements with it many advantages in impacting positively on the attitudes of people towards sustainable waste management.

Table 10: Factors affecting Plastic Waste Disposal

Variables	Mean	Decision
Poor wastebins	3.84	Accepted
Poor information	3.94	Accepted
Poor collection frequency	3.01	Accepted
Lack of smaller wastebins	2.20	Rejected

Source; Field Survey, 2022

Table 10 indicated that poor wastebins, information, and collection frequency are some of the factors militating against proper waste disposal in the metropolis

Conclusion

This study is designed to ascertain how broadcast media campaigns has helped in contributing to proper waste management in Enugu metropolis. Results showed that media campaigns have impacted positively on the attitudes of the residents of Enugu metropolis towards adopting proper waste disposal mechanism. It equally showed that media reportage of sustainable waste is insufficient and needs to be improved. Also, poor availability of wastebins, poor information, and poor collection frequency were listed as factors militating against proper waste disposal in the metropolis. We therefore, recommend that ESWAMA as a regulator

should organize periodically a public awareness campaign on radios to sensitize the public on the importance of proper plastic waste management mechanisms and the negative impact of improper waste disposal on health and the environment and Government should allocate resources to ESWAMA to enable its efficient and effective management of waste in the metropolis,

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